

FUELLING REGIONAL GROWTH: STILL A DREAM OR A CONCRETE POSSIBILITY?

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This paper was presented at the 14th Offshore Mediterranean Conference and Exhibition in Ravenna, Italy, March 27-29, 2019. It was selected for presentation by OMC 2019 Programme Committee following review of information contained in the abstract submitted by the author(s). The Paper as presented at OMC 2019 has not been reviewed by the Programme Committee.

ABSTRACT

In the framework of FP7 funding scheme, the project H2OCEAN (grant agreement n. 654871) has been developed, investigating a proof-of-concepts of a multi-use ocean platform, able to harvest energy, produce and store energy in the form of compressed H₂, together with a multi-trophic aquaculture and bio-waste treatment and drinkable water production.

The idea was to design a system able to convert renewable energy sources and biological conversions into **energy, food and water**, basics to ensure human health.

The challenge has been to stress the multi-use ocean platform to be stand alone, far from the shore, able to produce an excess of energy and water and obviously food and send them to the shore to be sold at a reasonable price. Special boats has been conceived to harvest energy from wind and waves, produce drinkable water for human use and for the electrolyser, special boats with alkaline electrolysers for oxygen and hydrogen generation and storage.

At a glance **figures** describing the ocean platform are: H₂ production: 74 kNm³/h and O₂ 37,5 kNm³/h. Aquaculture: 10 k ton/year. Drinkwater 20 m³/h. To achieve these KPIs, 95 Wave Energy converter and 67 Vertical Axis Wind turbines are included together with 34 aquaculture cages and support ships.

Issues are presented in this paper and are partially solved by a a real demonstration platform in the Project The Blue Growth Farm (grant agreement n. 774426). This pilot platform (20 x 20 m) will be build and tested at NOEL, located close to Strait of Messina. Test results will be utilised to scale-up the design of a larger floating platform able to harvest energy and breed certain species of fish and molluscs.

INTRODUCTION

The funded Project H2OCEAN had seventeen scientific and technical objectives. In this paper, we present part of them, specifically the development of a conceptual design engineering of integrated ocean deployment of energy harvesting, hydrogen generation, fish farm and fresh water production, thus enabling a Life Cycle Assessment and a cost estimate providing CAPEX and OPEX for a cost-benefit evaluation.

The purpose of the conceptual design was to provide figures and concepts to understand if it could be feasible (from cost point of view) a large offshore installation, 50 km far from the shore, able to provide energy, food and water.

We have designed the ocean deployment being formed by different parts, all interconnected, exchanging data, energy, materials.

These parts mainly are:

- WECs (wave energy converters)
- VAWTs (vertical axis wind turbines)
- Multi trophic aquaculture (fish and sea weeds)
- Desalinization plant (to produce “electrolysis grade” water and drinkable water)
- H₂ and O₂ generation (by means of large electrolysers)
- FAD (Floating anaerobic digester)

- EMCS (Energy, Management , Control System), logistic, safety

The conceptual design allowed to better understand the installation and a set of lessons learnt has been raised at the end. These lessons constitute information for next steps of engineering activities.

METHODOLOGY

A standard conceptual design methodology approach has been utilised, whose main steps are listed below:

- Definition of KPIs (Key performance indicators)
- Materials and energy balances
- Block Flow Diagrams
- Functional Lay out Diagram
- Process Flow Diagrams
- Equipment list
- Process lay outs and sea deployment

The definition of Key Performance Indicators, also known as User Requirement Specification (URS), allows the identification of main features and requirements in term of production rates and external constraints such as distances from the shore.

In the case of H2OCEAN project, KPIs are presented in table 1:

Tab. 1: Key Performance Indicators

Indicator/requirement	Figures	Notes
Country	Portugal	50 km from the shore
Wind speed @10 m	11.5 m/s	average
Wave energy	12.5 kW/m	
Wave energy	20.47 kW/m	1 year average
Working hours	7300 hours / year	per year
Hydrogen flow rate	74000 Nm ³ /h	Production rate
Oxygen flow rate	37000 Nm ³ /h	Production rate
H ₂ refuelling ship (rate)	5 days	
O ₂ refuelling ship (rate)	5 days	
H ₂ compression pressure	200 barg	
O ₂ compression pressure	200 bar g	
VAWT power	6.2 MW	Rated mechanical power
Number of VAWT per WEC	1	
Fish production	10000 tons /year	Per year
Fish species	Sea Bass	
Waste treatment capacity	4200 kg/day	
Drinking water production	20 m ³ /h	

An overview of the overall system is shown in figure 1, where energy and material flows are highlighted to show correlations among units.

Fig 1: Block Units with energy/material flows

Starting from the overall structure, material and energy flows are estimated, considering conversion rates, consumptions of energy and water, gas production.

The sea deployment has been divided into units, as presented in table 2:

Tab. 2: Key Performance Indicators

Unit	Description
U1	VAWT & WEC - Electrical Energy Production
U2	Water pre-treatment
U3	Desalination Unit RO1
U4	Drinking Water - Bladder
U5	DEMI Water Production RO2
U6	Hydrogen Generation
U7	Oxygen Storage - Fuel Station - Ship
U8	Compressed Hydrogen Storage - Fuel Station - Ship
U9	Fish Farm - Fish Farm Utilities - Ship
U10	FAD (Floating Anaerobic Digester) Reactor
U11	EMCS

Block Flow Diagrams have been prepared, at least one for each unit. The BFD are linked each other and has been reviewed several times by the consortium.

All Project partners have provided data and information utilised, integrated and coherently assembled in a excel file that has allowed the estimate of materials and energy flows and a first estimate of number of equipment and systems and their sizing.

Work Centre Summary (WCS) aggregates information coming from BFD preparing the subsequent activities: Function lay out diagram and Process Flow Diagram. Figure 2 presents WCS of Unit 2, water pre-treatment.

Unit U2 – Water Pre-treatment

The Unit 2, i.e. the water Pre-Treatment, is constituted by the following modules. This chapter contains also the main features of equipment, such as the volume, the installed power, the dimensions and the flow.

2 Sea Water Intake Pumps @5 bar (installed total power= 55 kWe, overall flow= 259 m³/h)

1 Sodium hypochlorite dosing pump system (specific power= 6 kWh/m³, flow= 5 l/h)

1 Sodium hypochlorite tank (volume= 3,7 m³)

2 Back Wash Pressure Pump @2,5 bar (total: installed power= 37 kWe, flow= 269 m³/h)

2 SWRO Low Pressure Pump @4 bar (each pump: installed power= 22 kWe, flow= 112, m³/h)

88 Ultrafiltration Units (flow= 240 m³/h)

1 Ultrafiltration Storage Tank (volume= 58 m³)

The Water Pre-Treatment is installed on-board the ship S0201.

Fig 2: Work Centre Summary of Unit 2 – water pre-treatment

Functional lay out defines the relationship among units and defines the structures that host equipment and systems offshore:

- Stationary fixed Platform
- FPSO
- Stationary fixed (e.g. buoy and sub-sea systems)

Fig 3: Different structures hosting equipment and systems

Process Flow Diagrams (PDFs) have been prepared crossing to the information coming from previous documents and knowledge coming from Consortium Partners. A total of 18 PDFs, describing process systems, have been delivered, Figure 4 presents PFD of water pre-treatment.

Fig 4: PFD of Water pre-treatment

Equipment list identifies items, systems, ships included in the sea deployment. Each of them (or group of similar equipment) are tagged and described. In addition, main features are indicated together with the quantity of each equipment, the dimension of one equipment and the installation area. It can be utilised as a bill of material for many engineering activities. In addition, a unique tag code identifies items in the lay out, the process descriptions, the data sheets, the Process Flow Diagrams. As shown in table 3, items are linked to a “package” (assemble of items), with short descriptions and features, quantities, dimensions and installation area, in this case onboard ship S0201 “water production ship”.

Tab. 3: Part of equipment list, Unit 2 (water pre-treatment)

Package	Item	Description	Features	Item qu'ty	Dimensions [m]	Installation Area
S0201		Water production ship (including EMCS)		1		
Y0201A	P0201 A/B	Sea Water Pump	55 kWe 245 m ³ /h 6 bar (30 kW installed)	2		Onboard S0201
Y0201A	T0201A	Storage Tank Raw Water	60 m ³	1	3,3x 3,3 x6,6	Onboard S0201
Y0201A	X0202A	UF System	229,4 m ³ /h			Onboard S0301

A Layout presents the overall arrangement of items on-board ships, with side view to improve understanding of the assembly. Figure 5 shows ship S0201 with the layout of items relevant unit 2 water pre-treatment.

Fig 5: Layout of items onboard S0201, including water pre-treatment unit

Figure 6 shows the side view of ship S0201, including water pre-treatment and large bladder storage and water filling area. In this ship, seawater is sucked, treated and temporary stored. By means of umbilical demineralised water is sent to electrolyzers (on-board ship S0601), while drinking water is fed to water bladders. Once filled, the bladders can be towed to shore.

Fig 6: Side view of items on-board S0201, including water pre-treatment unit

Nineteen layouts and sections of ships and one sea deployment layout, describing the overall installation offshore have been delivered.

Some figures describing the sea deployment: the wind farm covers a large rectangular area 11 km by 5 km (the upper part in figure 7), while the bottom part is occupied by water production ship, fish farms, hydrogen and oxygen production ship and gas storage ships.

Fig 7: Sea deployment

LESSON LEARNT AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE ACTIVITIES DERIVED FROM H2OCEAN PROJECT

As explained before, the installation is huge and involves a great number of systems.

In accordance with another project document “Full capital, maintenance and cost of ownership evaluation” that has analysed the conceptual design to extract data and economic impact in term of CAPEX and OPEX it can be concluded that the investment cost for such an installation can reach 6.67 billion euro (not considering replacement of equipment).

In order to build the whole installation many years can be necessary and a number of yard ships, in order to build 95 WEC and 4 Floating Process units, 2 gas storage ships and 3 carries, needs to be involved.

Currently the realisation of this sea deployment seems not imminent, because many parts have still a low TRL (technology readiness level) and some systems have never been assembled in such configuration.

When conceiving the installation, one of the requirements was to have an unmanned sea deployment. During the development of the project, it appeared clear that the “unmanned installation” was in contrast with the need to assure a constant scheduled maintenance of the

equipment and ships that are in the sea deployment. In addition, the deployment is far from the coast and any intervention from the coast takes a couple of hours by boat or 15 minutes flight with a helicopter (but this could be more expensive than the boat). Regarding maintenance, another project deliverable (D 8.4) stressed the scheduled maintenance: when reaching the end of the list of equipment under maintenance it's time to restart from the beginning. In any case, automatic devices cannot perform maintenance and human operators are needed to solve issues in the offshore deployment. The living quarter boat hosts a maintenance facility to ease the maintenance works, avoiding unnecessary up and down of maintenance crew.

Moreover, security issues suggest keeping people offshore to protect the installation and prevent external attacks.

The sea deployment requires 250 km of seabed umbilical to collect electric energy generated by WECs and VAWTs. With just 50 km, it is possible to reach the coast and distribute power to the shore, when randomly produced by energy harvesters (WEC and VAWT). In this way, the production of hydrogen can be done onshore, instead of offshore thus avoiding problems of offshore gas production, offshore maintenance and offshore safety.

One single WEC, coupled with aquaculture can satisfy energy needs of an array of cages.

A big issue is the enormous quantity of sea feed that shall be transported from the coast to the sea deployment (about 18000 tonnes per year).

Multi trophic aquaculture is not working since it doesn't provide any benefit (but also no drawbacks).

In addition, no benefits come when utilizing oxygen to enrich it in aquaculture water. Oxygen enrichment can work in a closed tub, not in the open sea due to currents that disperse the gas and organic matters that react with oxygen.

A special ship for water generation has been conceived. It includes two basins for filling of water bladders in a protected area prior to release into the sea.

A process layout based on multiple levels has been proposed for the electrolyser ship. It has been decided and designed to collect oxygen and sell it, instead of vent (as done usually). A modification of the electrolysis process and oxygen collection has been proposed.

It is worth to consider that the first two levels of the ship are under the sea level and this fact complicates the safety aspects regarding the risk of explosion, release of energy and structure collapse. This issue could be solved in the next steps of engineering design.

The sea deployment could have a "dual use" since (when available) there is a lot of energy, gaseous hydrogen and oxygen, fish (food) and drinkable water, and the possibility to discharge solid wastes.

This vast installation may create interferences with navigation routes, since it obliges ships to circumnavigate it: it is not possible to cross the energy harvesting area while VAWT are running for safety reasons.

It should be noted that this kind of offshore installation may generate benefit onshore in the port area, since large quantities of hydrogen, oxygen, water, fish reach the shore and are processed at regional level.

NEXT STEP: THE BLUE GROWTH FARM

Thanks to the experience of H2OCEAN project, European Commission (grant n. 774428) has granted a new research project, namely The Blue Growth Farm. In this project a pilot platform (scaled down) will be build, allowing the testing of caissons' junctions and scaled down systems. Data observed and retrieved from this pilot will be utilised for the design of a large installation that is planned to be 120 m by 100 m, with energy harvesters (wave and wind), fish farm and energy transport onshore.

This project has 10 technical and non technical objectives, such as "To design a low-cost, corrosion-resistant, low-maintenance modular concrete floating multi-purpose offshore platform,

capable of accommodating aquaculture, wind and wave energy systems and then to test and validate this design through the construction and sea deployment a pilot scale platform”.

The construction and testing of the pilot concrete platform is foreseen in Italy at NOEL (Natural Ocean Engineering Laboratory), close to Strait of Messina.

With “The Blue Growth Farm” the goals set by the notional project H2OCEAN will do a step forward, with the concrete construction of the pilot platform at NOEL. Once the large scale platform will be built, combined aquaculture, power harvesting and distribution will be able to fuel the growth at regional level.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper an overview of engineering activities related to H2OCEAN project is presented. In addition, the follow up project “The blue growth farm” and its objectives and features are described. Some issues raised in H2OCEAN project have been challenged by The Blue Growth farm project, trying to overcome technical barriers and provide enabling technologies for ocean exploitation, feeding energy and materials at regional level.

At the end, fuelling regional growth is no more a dream but is not a concrete possibility yet: just work in progress.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The mentioned projects, H2OCEAN and The Blue Growth Farm have received funding from European Commission, respectively Grant Agreement no. 654871 and no. 774426.

I also recall the efforts and the information provided from of all consortium Partners of H2OCEAN Project, specifically: Armando J. Palomar and Maria Navarro from AWS Truepower, Ian Hart from BHR Group, David Torrijos from SETA, Andreas Huebscher from ISL, Gino Bawn and Sonal Fricker from ITP. Tim Atack from Viking Fish Farm, Giulio Brizzi from Chlamis, Mario Rosato from Sustainable Technologies, Anders Kohler and Sarah Bellew from Floating Power Plant, Stephen Divers from Fusion Marine.

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